

«STUDIES OF LOW-RIGID CYLINDRICAL PARTS. TYPES OF PRODUCTS, OPERATING CONDITIONS, WAYS TO IMPROVE THEIR QUALITY»

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***Annotation:** Among the various machine parts, over 30% are bodies of revolution, of which the most labor-intensive and difficult to manufacture are parts with low rigidity. The rigidity of a shaft is judged by the ratio of its length (L) to its diameter (D). In this article, we have studied some low-rigid cylindrical parts, types of these products, operating conditions and ways to improve their quality.*

***Keywords:** Rotation body, shaft, long shaft, heat treatment, chemical-thermal treatment.*

The rigidity of a shaft is judged by the ratio of its length (l) to its diameter (D): $k = l/D$ where $k = 3...5$ rigid shafts, $k = 5...10$ — shafts of medium = $10...12$ and more low rigidity [6,61,119]. Low-rigid parts are used in the automotive, mining, aviation industries, in machine tool and instrument making, in shipbuilding, in oil, chemical, agricultural, and power engineering. Low-rigid parts include drive and running shafts, axles, cylindrical guides, rods, plungers, sleeves, valves, cylinders, pump plungers, transmission shafts, rollers for textile and agricultural machines, pipes for cardan shafts, cylinders shock absorbers and other long parts.

In most cases, such parts operate under alternating loads and experience sufficiently large elastic deformations of bending and torsion. At high speeds of rotation and insufficient rigidity of the shafts, even a very small curvature causes an imbalance, vibrations and an increase in dynamic loads on the supports, which significantly accelerates the destruction of parts and machines as a whole. During

operation, variable loads and temperature, friction forces in the presence of abrasive and various external factors act on the shafts. Under their action, the shaft as a whole and its individual surfaces are subject to deformation (bending, twisting, crushing), various types of wear (fatigue, oxidative, molecular-mechanical, corrosion-mechanical, abrasive, etc.) and destruction.

Finishing long shafts (length to diameter ratio over 10) is one of the most labor-intensive operations. This is due to the low rigidity of the workpiece, vibrations, the difficulty of achieving the desired quality, accuracy and productivity, as well as the lack of the necessary equipment.

It is known that the state of the surface layer of shafts and other parts has a significant impact on the operational properties of machines. Special treatment can impart special physical and mechanical properties to the surface layers of machine parts. For this purpose, a number of methods are used in mechanical engineering. All these methods can be classified as follows:

- heat treatment (bulk hardening, surface hardening);
- chemical-thermal treatment (carburizing, nitrocarburizing, aluminizing, chromium plating, boriding, siliconizing, sulfiding);
- plastic deformation (shot blasting, centrifugal ball hardening, roller rolling, embossing).

The attention of scientists and production workers is attracted by the exceptional simplicity of implementing chipless technological processes: efficiency, economy, and the possibility of hardening parts during manufacture and in operation. Methods of surface plastic deformation have significant advantages over thermal and chemical-thermal types of hardening in terms of ease of implementation, accessibility, and effectiveness. Their main task is to provide the specified quality of the surface layer, which is characterized by its physical and mechanical properties and surface microgeometry.

In the manufacture of machine parts, surface plastic deformation (SPD) is used - pressure treatment, in which only the surface layer of the part material is plastically deformed. Surface plastic deformation is based on the ability of a metal

surface to accept residual plastic deformation without violating the integrity of the metal. Surface plastic deformation is one of the simplest and most effective technological ways to improve the performance and reliability of machine parts. The formation of a surface layer with desired properties should be ensured by hardening technology.

The method of surface hardening with its inherent compressive stresses has shown that it increases the resistance to the occurrence of plastic deformation during the operation of the part. At the same time, the tendency to the formation and development of fatigue cracks is weakened, and the resistance to abrasive wear and fretting corrosion increases.

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